

Existence of Positive Solutions for Second-Order Difference Equation with Discrete Boundary Value Problem

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Abstract : We study the existence of positive solutions to the three points difference summation boundary value problem. We show the existence of at least one positive solution if f is either superlinear or sublinear by applying the fixed point theorem due to Krasnoselskii in cones.

Keywords : positive solution, boundary value problem, fixed point theorem, cone

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